

NODES – Nord Ovest Digitale e Sostenibile

Energy studies and carbon footprint of farms

SPOKE 6 – PRIMARY AGROINDUSTRY

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This report provides an analysis of energy consumption, carbon footprint, and performance evaluation for two agricultural enterprises: Ent#1 “Azienda Agricola Le Colombaie S.r.l.” and Ent#2 “Cezoo Centro di Ricerche per la Zootecnia e l'Ambiente S.c.r.l.”, as part of the NODES project (Nord Ovest Digitale e Sostenibile). The goal is to assess the sustainability and efficiency of these farms using Key Performance Indicators (KPIs), with the wider aim of understanding their features to become part of an A-REC (Agricultural Renewable Energy Community). Both farms are highly technological with respect to the average farm, but they differ significantly in scale. This difference in size makes direct data comparison difficult, especially regarding energy consumption and production efficiency. As a result, we used KPIs to create a standardized, comparable framework for evaluating their performance and be able to extend their specific results to different cases.

Overview of KPIs:

- Economic KPI: Both farms meet industry benchmarks with similar costs per liter of milk produced.
- Energy KPI: Despite consuming significantly more energy, Ent#1 has a lower energy consumption per liter of milk than Ent#2, due to its larger production capability.
- Environmental KPI: on one hand Ent#2's use of renewable energy, through photovoltaic panels, reduces its carbon footprint. On the other, Ent#1's lower emissions per liter of milk reflect its larger scale and efficiency.

This analysis emphasizes the importance of KPIs in comparing diverse agricultural setups and suggests areas for improvement, particularly in energy consumption and environmental sustainability. The results can guide the optimization of performance in agricultural enterprises, enhance competitiveness in the sector, and contribute to a more sustainable agro-industry.

KPIs calculation

Case study

In comparison to the previous deliverables (1.1 and 1.2), the two chosen farms exhibit significant differences. Although both are highly technological and cutting-edge, Cerzoo, being mainly a research center, has a limited production capacity with only 100 cows, while Le Colombaie has 1,130, making it a medium-large farm. This difference in size complicates a direct comparison of the collected data. Variations in production scale and energy efficiency make it challenging to conduct an accurate comparative analysis. The data obtained (in blue) or provided (in green) by the farms are shown in Table 1 for Le Colombaie and in Table 2 for Cerzoo. In particular, the amount of milk obtained from each cow during each milking was calculated using the data provided by Le Colombaie and utilized for the calculations in the Cerzoo case.

POD	Description	Amount	Unit
Barn/Farm	No. Livestock	1,130	
	Barn/Farm electricity consumption	1,499,357	kWh/yr
	E. Consumption per cow	1,326.86	kWh/(yr*cow)
	Barn consumption costs	629,696.41	€/yr
	No. Milking per day	3.00	milking/day
	No. cows milked per day	3,390	
	Tot. milk produced per day	47,200	l/day
	Tot. milk produced per year	17,228,000	l/yr
	Average liters per cow per milking	13.92	l/(cow*milking)

Table 1: Energy data and indicators of Le Colombaie farm.

POD	Description	Amount	Unit
Barn/Farm	No. Livestock	100	
	Barn/Farm electricity consumption	235,024.59	kWh/yr
	E. consumption per cow	2,350.25	kWh/(yr*cow)
	Barn consumption costs	39,954.18	€/yr
	No. Milking per day	2.00	milking/day
	No. Cows milked per day	200	
	Tot. milk produced per day	2,784.66	l/day
	Tot. milk produced per year	1,016,401.18	l/yr
	Average liters per cow per milking	13.92	l/(cow*milking)

Table 2: Energy data and indicators of Cerzoo farm.

Key Performance Indicators: Why?

To address the issue of understanding the common path of their consumption, we decided to use “ad hoc” indicators, specifically adopting Key Performance Indicators (KPIs), which in general are tools for measuring organizational performance. According to Gosselin [1], KPIs are objective values that measure, compare, and manage an organization's effectiveness. They are essential benchmarks to assess whether a company is achieving its strategic goals. As highlighted by O'Reilly [2], the use of KPIs allows companies to identify strengths and weaknesses, fostering greater competitiveness within the industry by providing a clear view of their performance in various operational areas.

This methodology enables us to overcome the limitations related to the structural differences between the two farms and obtain an objective and comparable assessment of their performances.

State of Art

The literature reports numerous papers discussing the use of KPIs in the agro-livestock sector, particularly in relation to milk production. In [3] the authors analyze dairy farm intensification in the UK from 2001 to 2014 using farm survey data and KPIs. In [4], the work focuses on presenting the energy consumption of small farms that are less developed and technologized than medium/large farms, and therefore rely on different KPIs to show the relevance of the features. Additionally, in [5], the authors examine the global use of electricity on dairy farms, highlighting that the main sources of consumption are the milking and cooling phases of milk. They use KPIs to make analyses and comparisons between farms worldwide. In [6] the authors propose a general set of sustainability indicators to help companies assess their environmental, social, and governance performance, with environmental indicators accounting for almost half of the common indicators extracted. The focus of our analysis primarily centers on papers [4] and [5] as they are currently most relevant to our research.

KPIs

The key performance indicators that we consider most relevant are those related to economic, environmental and energy aspects.

Economic KPI

It's important to note that we approximated the density of milk to be 1 kg/dm³. The economic KPI is based on the cost of producing one liter of milk. In reference [4], the authors obtained a value of 0.04 €/l. This means that, on average, 0.04 € is spent by the companies for each liter of milk produced. When comparing this KPI with the values from our case studies in Table 3, we can see that both Cerzoo and Le Colombaie meet this value, despite the fact that a few years have gone and Countries (although located in Europe) are different.

Farm	Description	Amount	Unit
Le Colombaie	Milk production costs	0.037	€/l
	Milk production consumption	0.087	kWh/l
Cezoo	Milk production costs	0.039	€/l
	Milk production consumption	0.231	kWh/l

Table 3: Economic KPIs for Le Colombaie and Cezoo.

Energy KPI

The indicator that shows information on energy use is the kWh consumed by the farm to produce one liter of milk. This helps us understand the company's energy consumption relative to its milk production. The energy KPI is influenced by many factors and cannot be one-size-fits-all. In general, larger companies tend of course to show lower specific KPIs. In fact, in [4], they establish a range for energy consumption between 0.32 and 3.99 MJ/kg (i.e. 0.089÷1.108 kWh/l), a range which is confirmed in our case studies, as reported in Table 4.

Farm	Description	Amount	Unit
Le Colombaie	Electricity consumed to produce 1 liter of milk	0.087	kWh/l
Cezoo	Electricity consumed to produce 1 liter of milk	0.23	kWh/l

Table 4: Energy KPIs for Le Colombaie and Cezoo.

For Le Colombaie 0.087 kWh/l represents the lower limit of the range.

Le Colombaie consumes six times more energy than Cezoo. However, Cezoo produces about 6% of Le Colombaie's annual milk production. This production discrepancy, due to the size of the farm and the number of livestock, leads Le Colombaie to have a KPI about fifteen times lower, despite consuming much more than Cezoo.

Even in the paper [5] that focuses mainly on energy, this concept is reiterated. They show how the KPI varies according to farm size, with small farms (≤ 100 head) having higher values than medium/large farms. They report a range from 2.6 to 23.4 kWh*100/l. So again, the values from our case studies are within the range. We note again that Le Colombaie is very close to the lower limit and Cezoo to the upper limit.

Environmental KPI

The environmental KPI refers to the kilos of CO₂ emitted into the atmosphere for each liter of milk produced by the company. This KPI is highly dependent on the type of energy source used for the production process. Our calculation is based only on CO₂ emissions based on electricity consumption and does not consider:

- Direct emissions from animal husbandry: Methane (CH₄) from the cows' digestive processes and nitrous oxide (N₂O) from manure.
- Indirect emissions: Feed production and transport, fertilizer and pesticide use.
- Emissions from processing and transport: Energy used for pasteurization, packaging, transport, and refrigeration.

Due to these factors, the KPI values we obtained are lower than those reported in the literature. To calculate the KPI, we use conversion factors that vary depending on the energy source. For renewable sources like solar, the factor is zero, while for electricity, in Italy, it is 0.25 kgCO₂/kWh [7].

Farm	Description	Amount	Unit
Le Colombaie	kgCO ₂ per liter of milk produced with electricity	0.02176	kgCO ₂ /l
Cerzoo	kgCO ₂ per liter of milk produced with electricity	0.05781	kgCO ₂ /l

Table 5: Environmental KPIs for Le Colombaie and Cerzoo.

Cerzoo is the only barn among our two case studies to use renewable resources; it has a photovoltaic system installed on the roofs of the barn. The system data are shown in Table 6.

POD	Description	Amount	Unit
Photovoltaic	No. PV panels installed	288	
	Single panel power	0.32	kW
	Plant power	92.16	kW
	Energy produced per year	101,376.00	kWh/yr

Table 6: Photovoltaic system data of Cerzoo farm.

As a matter of fact, the electricity generated by photovoltaic panels can reduce the KPI of Table 7 almost to half of the original value, of what reported in Table 5. Because of the size, Le Colombaie, which does not use any renewable resource yet, can still manage to achieve a lower environmental KPI than Cerzoo. But the gap is almost filled. This observation makes the definition of novel KPIs urgent: for instance, by the means of an indicator which strictly relates

the renewable yearly production to the unit of headage (kWh/(cow.year)). This would favor the value in using renewables, while comparing farms, thus providing a boost in moving towards more sustainable energy uses.

Farm	Description	Amount	Unit
Cerzoo	kgCO ₂ per l of milk produced with electricity considering photovoltaics	0.033	kgCO ₂ /l

Table 7: Photovoltaic system data of Cerzoo farm.

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